

Management control and job satisfaction. The mediating effect of personality traits.

Santini, F.^{a} Griep, Y.J.L.^b Cotana, M.L.^c*

^{a,c} Department. of Economics (UNIPG); ^b Behavioural Science Institute (Radboud University, Netherlands)

** Corresponding Author*

Key-words: management control; personality traits; job satisfaction; COR theory.

JEL-codes: M10, M50

Introduction

Based on the COR theory, people are motivated to acquire, protect, and foster the acquisition of the resources they value (Hobfoll, 1988). Psychological resources affect emotional well-being (Hobfoll and Wells, 1998). In this regard, management controls, which includes all the devices and systems managers use to ensure that the decisions of their employees are consistent with the organization's objectives and strategies (Malmi and Brown, 2008), might be perceived by people with different personality traits as the cause of resource gain or loss, thus leading to differing emotions and job satisfaction.

This study focuses on the emotional consequences of management controls – as mediated by personality traits – and their effect on job satisfaction.

Methods

A survey will be submitted to a sample of 1,000 employees from multiple organizations. A hierarchical regression, including some control variables, will be applied. Mediation of personality traits will be tested using Baron and Kenny's (1986) regression technique.

The analysis performed on the actual working conditions of employees will be double-tested through questions about the changes in the work routines (e.g., remote working) driven by the COVID-19 pandemic.

Conservation of Resources Theory (COR) and Big Five Theory are adopted as they fit the idea that individuals showing different personality traits should prefer almost some different psychological resources.

Results

We expect to check the underlying dynamics over three main research hypotheses: 1) There is a relationship between management controls and psychological resources, which is mediated by personality traits. 2) There

is a relationship between stress and the gap between desired and actual levels of resources, which is mediated by personality traits; 3) There is a relationship between the level of stress and job satisfaction, which is mediated by personality traits.

The idea that Job satisfaction is a driver of Job performance is widely accepted in management control and organization literature. In this regard, this paper aims to help organizations to achieve superior performance while assuring improved working conditions.

References

- Achnak, S., Griep, Y., Vantilborgh, T., 2018. I am so tired... How fatigue may exacerbate stress reactions to psychological contract breach. *Frontiers in Psychology* 9, 1-15.
- Baron, R. M., Kenny, D. A., 1986. The moderator–mediator variable distinction in social psychological research: Conceptual, strategic, and statistical considerations. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology* 51, 1173–1182.
- Hobfoll, S. E., 1989. Conservation of resources: a new Attempt at conceptualizing stress. *Am. Psychol.* 44, 513–524.
- Malmi, T., Brown, D., 2008. Management control systems as a package—Opportunities, challenges and research directions. *Management Accounting Research* 19, 287-300.
- McCrae, R. R., Costa, P. T., Jr., 2008. The five-factor theory of personality. In John, O. P., Robins, R. W., Pervin, L. A. (Eds.), *Handbook of personality: Theory and research* (pp. 159–181). The Guilford Press, New York.
- Wibbeke, L.M., Lachmann, M., 2020. Psychology in management accounting and control research: an overview of the recent literature. *Journal of Management Control* 31, 275-328.

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10053989